

If AI Could Evolve Recursively, Why Not Humans?

Abstract

Discussions about modern so-called artificial intelligence [AI] often lead to questions about artificial general intelligence [AGI], an entity far surpassing human capabilities. This idea is based on the concept of recursive or logarithmic self-improvement: that the machine could replace its base code faster and faster, quickly reaching a level of "super intelligence" incomprehensible to humanity. This short essay does not address the feasibility of this possibility, but instead focuses on a different perspective: If we are willing to believe that AI could evolve recursively, why not humans?

Keywords: artificial intelligence, artificial general intelligence, intelligence, recursive self-improvement, philosophy of technology, epistemic limits

“Neural Networks”

It is well-known that machine "neural networks" are inspired by biological neural networks. Despite this fact, there seems to be no serious consideration of the possibility that humans themselves could vastly improve themselves cognitively. Why is the assumption that humans have reached a limit, and that technology would be necessary for overcoming it? Indeed, humanity seems to have already undergone a recursive evolution since the formulation of the scientific method. Most people agree that humanity's improvements for the last few centuries are on orders of magnitude greater than all past millennia. If AI was not necessary then, why would it be necessary now?

There are a few possible coherent answers to this question:

1. The main one may be about scale: Unlike humans, machines can simultaneously use entire fields of processing units. However, this assumes intelligence is a matter of size. By this logic, whales, whose brains are the size of cars, would be hundreds of times smarter than humans, yet they are not. If there is anything we should have

learned from AI so far, it is that throwing processing power and data at it is insufficient.

2. Another possible answer is about speed: The technology would be able to use available information to reach conclusions vastly faster. However, this introduces a fundamental limitation that is rarely mentioned: If we cannot verify the output for any reason, then how can we know it is reasonable? One might then answer: "Based on results!" And then the question becomes, is the philosophy of "what's the worst that can happen" reasonable? Are results always worth the cost?...

Many people seem to be willing to take an existential risk, but for what? Why is human intelligence assumed to be insufficient? One might think that "machines can rewrite their own code; humans cannot rewrite their brains." That is precisely the premise put into question. Is that a statement of fact or faith? What is its basis? Have you tried and failed to rewrite your brain? Do people even allow themselves to ask the fundamental questions, to change their mentality fundamentally?

- If the answer is no, then that is clearly the actual limitation.
- If the answer is yes, then why do you not improve yourself recursively?